

Spot the learning

Five common learning difficulties have been identified in mainstream schools. Help your child overcome them with these tips.

By Dr Noel Chia Kok Hwee

What are learning difficulties? These must not be confused with learning disabilities, learning disorders, learning differences, learning disadvantages and learning dysfunctions. All these terms mean different things. According to Australia's National Health and Medical Research Council, "learning difficulties" is a generic term referring to those who manifest problems in developmental and academic skills, and these difficulties can be the result of intellectual disability, physical and sensory defects, emotional difficulties, inadequate environmental experiences, and lack of appropriate educational opportunities.

It is not always necessary for children with learning difficulties to attend a special school. They can be helped during normal curricular time by a learning support teacher or outside school hours to attend special classes conducted by an allied

educator who provides learning and behavioural support (previously known as a special needs officer). Depending on the kind of learning difficulty and its degree of severity, teachers, allied educators and parents can all play their respective roles in helping their children cope with daily learning challenges.

Perhaps what is most important is to develop an awareness of common learning difficulties encountered by children in school. We must also be aware of the fact that every child is unique. Each has his or her style of learning and may not click well with the normal teaching style in school. If these differences are severe enough, they result in learning difficulties.

Five Main Areas of Learning Difficulties

Here I have listed only the two main areas (there are many more) of potential learning

difficulties: sensory processing difficulties and executive function difficulties. The three important sensory processing difficulties are auditory (aural and oral) processing difficulties, visual-spatial processing difficulties, and written output difficulties. The two important executive function difficulties are the executive skill difficulties and attention-concentration difficulties. Let me discuss briefly the symptoms of each of them:

Sensory Processing Difficulties

1. Auditory (Aural and Oral) Processing Difficulties

These difficulties happen when a child has difficulty processing the meaning of language. Aural processing difficulties refer to listening problems, while oral processing difficulties concern speaking problems. Such children have normal hearing acuity and display no speech delay. However,

they have difficulty understanding what is being spoken or presenting their thoughts in spoken language. They also display the following symptoms:

- Difficulties in comprehending or recalling what has been said or taught;
- Difficulties in following oral instructions and executing multiple-step oral directions or instructions correctly;
- Confusion with similar sounding words (e.g., shot and short);
- Poor phonological skills (in this case, the child might be dyslexic but has not been diagnosed formally);
- Daydreaming during lessons (in this case, the child might have an attention-related

the symptoms of visual-spatial processing difficulties are:

- Forgetfulness or difficulties in recalling things they have seen;
- Inability or poor ability to copy accurately from whatever the teacher has written on the board;
- Loud reading or mumbling a given passage when doing reading comprehension and hence, disturbing others sitting nearby;
- Difficulties in solving mathematical problems, especially in tessellations, trigonometry and geometry;
- Difficulties in spelling;
- Difficulties in handwriting; and

challenges!

learning difficulty);

- Difficulties in presenting ideas or explaining oneself clearly in spoken form;
- Mental and/or physical fatigue; and
- Slow processing of auditory information (e.g., when a question is asked).

What can be done: In class, the teacher can give preferential seating for students with auditory processing difficulties. When teaching, it is good to use visual reinforcement of oral information. Repeat the key points covered in the lesson or invite the student to repeat the essential information.

Both parents and teachers may want to speak slowly so that time is given for the student with such a challenging issue to process the information. Also, reducing environmental noise level and allowing extra time for such students to complete their given tasks will help too.

2. Visual-Spatial Processing Difficulties

Children with visual-spatial processing difficulties often perform badly in reading comprehension. However, they can be highly verbal and depend on their auditory channel and auditory memory to assist them in discussion and lecture settings. Some of

- Poor visualising ability or poor visual-spatial perception.

What can be done: Teachers can provide auditory reinforcement during lessons, discussions and lectures. If specific academic help is required, tutoring might be needed in those areas the students are weak in. It is good if teachers and parents can provide hands-on experience as such an approach can help students with visual-spatial processing difficulties to supplement their weaknesses. Allow the students the use of computers to compose and edit their written assignments. Giving them extra time to complete their given tasks is also most helpful.

3. Written Output Difficulties

Children who have normal oral expression but are unable to put their thoughts in a properly written form are described as having written output difficulties. They have lots of interesting ideas but encounter a stumbling block in putting their ideas onto paper. Hence, written assignments are always a nightmare to them. Several research studies suggest that, for some reason, the mind-motor connection is not forged strongly, resulting in a weak written output. In other words, the mind says one thing, but the hands do another thing.

“Perhaps what is most important is to develop an awareness of common learning difficulties encountered by children in school. We must also be aware of the fact that every child is unique. Each has his or her style of learning and may not click well with the normal teaching style in school. If these differences are severe enough, they result in learning difficulties.”

What can be done: It is good if writing assignments are broken down into workable chunks so as to allow such students to organise their ideas, talk about them, and then put them down on paper. Teachers may want to encourage these students to do peer editing or self-editing through the procedure of edit, edit and then edit again. Written assignments can be done successfully if students find the topics interesting and meaningful to them. Allow extra time and use of a computer for these students to complete their written work. Finally, both teachers and parents should focus more on the process of learning rather than the product which is an end of learning in itself.

Executive Function Difficulties

4. Executive Skill Difficulties

Children with executive skill difficulties are messy and poor time managers. They keep losing their things (e.g., textbooks and pencils). They have difficulty paying attention in class and beyond in ordering their thoughts, their materials, and their daily activities. Their written assignments are often untidy or disorganised. These children may also have visual-spatial processing difficulties. Hence, they will find reading comprehension, mathematics and creative writing particularly tough to complete. Executive skill difficulties include the following:

- Poor ability to create a roadmap to reach a goal or complete a task;
- Poor ability to arrange or place things according to a proper system;
- Difficulties in estimating how much time one has, how to allocate it, and how to stay within time limits and deadlines;
- Difficulties in holding information in mind while performing complex tasks, to draw from past learning experience to apply to the situation at hand, and to problem-solve in the future; and
- Poor ability to stand back and take a bird's eye view of oneself in a situation, observe how to problem-solve an issue, self-monitor progress, and self-evaluate one's performance.

What can be done: Parents and teachers can organise a realistic time schedule for such

students to follow. Use graphic organisers such as charts, diagrams and figures to assist these students in their learning. Thinking and studying strategies such as mind-mapping, scaffolding and study skills are also useful tools for these students to acquire and use in their daily studies.

5. Attention-Concentration Difficulties

Attention and arousal are two of our most fundamental abilities. They form our complex, multi-faceted attention-concentration system. Children with attention-concentration difficulties often encounter problems in sustaining attention or concentration and/or in inhibiting themselves. Self-regulation becomes a challenging issue. Research studies show that the ability to self-regulate is to be able to sustain and inhibit, and this ability is closely linked to neurotransmitters in our brain. Neurotransmitters are chemicals that carry neural messages from one neuron (brain cell) to another. If there are not enough of these transmitters (e.g., dopamine), a neural breakdown happens resulting in an attention-concentration deficit. Children with such severe problems are often described as having attention deficit-hyperactivity disorder (ADHD for short). Medication (e.g., Ritalin) and various intensive attention training programmes have been found to be effective when dealing with these difficulties. The following are some common symptoms of attention-concentration difficulties:

- Difficulties in attending to details;
- Making many careless mistakes in school-work or other activities;
- Difficulties in organising tasks and activities;
- Easily distracted by environmental stimuli;
- Reluctance in engaging in activities that require sustained mental effort; and
- Difficulties in following through instructions and failure to complete given tasks.

What can be done: For parents and teachers with such students, it is always important to remember to maintain eye contact when talking with these students and keep oral directions short and simple. Also, when presenting information, do so in a variety of communicative modes and

keep distractions to a minimum. It would be good to allow students with attention-concentration difficulties to explain how they learn, and derive their answer to a question, and tape record lectures or lessons for later or future review.

Advice for parents and teachers

The first step is to acknowledge that learning difficulties can happen to any child. It is therefore, important to understand what learning difficulties are and how they affect our children in their learning process. It is also good for parents and teachers to observe if their children display some of the symptoms described above. Parents and teachers should take time to visit a public library or a bookstore to search for books related to these learning difficulties.

The internet is the best source of information if they need to find out more about a specific learning difficulty. Through reading and information searches on the internet, they will understand the struggles their children with such challenging issues are facing in school or at home. Many books offer useful advice, tips and strategies that parents can use to help their children.

Another important step is to seek professional assistance such as visiting a psychologist for a diagnostic assessment to be done or a counsellor/social worker for help and referral. Whatever that follows, depending on the type and the severity of the learning difficulty, always seek professional advice from a qualified special needs therapist or an educational therapist for intervention. The therapist will design and conduct a special individualised education programme (IEP) catering to the child's learning needs.

Finally, parents must be prepared to collaborate with teachers and other professionals to help their children. They must be proactive to take an interest in their children's social-emotional well-being and their academic performance. Children with learning difficulties need a lot of patience and understanding from their parents and teachers. Without the adult support, these children may quickly lose self-confidence and eventually develop low self-esteem.

Dr Noel Chia Kok Hwee is the assistant professor, Early Childhood Special Needs Education, National Institute of Education.